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Scientific Study of Language in Ancient India

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Language study is that area of knowledge where the ancient Indians have contributed to a commendable extent. The early speculations about the nature of language are to be traced as early as in the Vedic period. The language was considered to be of divine origin. The R̥gveda (RV 8.100.11) (circa 2000 BCE) the earliest form of sacred literature mentions:

*devīm vācam ajanayanta devās tāmi viśvārūpāḥ paśāvo vadanti |
sā no mandrēṣam ūrjāṃ dūhānā dhenūr vāg asmān ūpa sūṣṭutaitu ||*

“The gods created this divine speech which is spoken in by various beings. Let that cow, who is well-praised bestowing vigour and strength approach us.”

For the ancient Vedic ṛṣis (seers) language was much more than a simple means of communication. Speech or language, for them, was of divine origin and they sought to gain the grace of the speech. The seers considered it to be an effective means of gratifying the deities in the nature like Agni (fire), Indra (thunderbolt), Marut (winds), etc. Subsequently, prime importance was given to the accurate usage of speech without even a smallest variation in a letter, accent or length. It was strongly believed that a mantra if uttered erroneously would bring harm to the performer as it would not convey the intended meaning. The compound *indraśatru* can be dissolved in two ways based on the accent as *indrasya śatruḥ*, the slayer of Indra and *indraḥ śatruḥ yasya*, one whose slayer is Indra.

See, Pāṇinīyaśikṣā 52:

*matro hīnaḥ svarato varṇato vā mithyāprayukto na tam artham āha |
sa vāgvajro yajamānaṃ hinasti yathendraśatruḥ svarato 'parādhāt ||*

“A mantra uttered either with a defective accent or pronunciation is badly done and it does not carry the proper sense. And it is like a thunderbolt of speech and kills the performer just as ‘*indraśatru*’ did on account of its wrong accent.”

Further, it was also believed that utterance of a single correct word would lead to the obtainment of heaven. There is a statement apparently from a Vedic text not available to us. It is found cited by Jayantabhaṭṭa in his Nyāyamañjarī (ii.230.10) and also by Kaiyaṭa in his commentary Pradīpa on Vyākaraṇamahābhāṣya (36B.8-9):

ekaḥ śabdaḥ samyak jñataḥ suprayuktaḥ sarge loke kāmādugh bhavati |

“A word known in a correct manner and used properly, becomes a wish-fulfilling cow in heaven (due to acquired merit).”

The sacred language of the Vedas became an important inheritance of preservation. This position lead to the necessity of language study in details, which further developed into six ancillary sciences called Vedāṅgas, viz. the Śikṣās (study of speech sounds), Nirukta (derivation of words), Vyākaraṇa (grammar), Chandas (prosody), Kalpa (rituals)

and Jyitoṣa (astronomy). They belong to the first millennia BCE. Among these, the Śikṣās, Nirukta, and Vyākaraṇa (grammar) directly relate to the analysis of language. In this analysis, a *varṇa* (speech sound) was recognized as the smallest unit. The Śikṣās and Prātiśākhya thoroughly describe the articulatory process of the *varṇas*. Pāṇinīyaśikṣā (circa 400 BCE) states in details the production of speech. It says:

*ātmanā buddhyā sametyārthān mano yuñke vivakṣayā |
manaḥ kāyāgnim āhanti sa prerayati mārutam |
mārutas tūrasī caran mandraṁ janayate svaram||*
(Pāṇinīyaśikṣā 6-7a)

“The *ātman* (soul) with intellect perceives things and sets the mind to an intention of speaking; the mind (then) gives impetus to the fire within the body, and the latter drives the breath out. The breath circulating within the lungs creates the soft tone.”

This provides for the pulmonic air stream mechanism of modern phonetics. The Śikṣās describe the places and manners of articulation of all the possible speech sounds. They describe the features of phonation, nasalization, aspiration, state of glottis, length of vowels and so on. To record the accuracy of pronunciation, Pāṇinīyaśikṣā provides analogies of bird and animal sounds which were familiar to common people, e.g.

*cāṣas tu vadati mātrāṁ dvimātrāṁ caiva vāyasaḥ |
śikhī rauti trimātrāṁ tu nakulas tv ardhāmātrakam||*
(Pāṇinīyaśikṣā 49)

“The *cāṣa* (blue jay) gives out one *mātrā* and the crow two *mātrās*, the peacock three *mātrās* and the mungoose only a half *mātrā*”

The Śikṣās are thus rightly described as the manual of phonetics. The Prātiśākhya mainly record the variations or marginal differences in pronunciation, rules and exceptions of Sandhis, accents, etc. They are important records of separate branches of the Vedas.

The sacred Vedic texts or Saṁhitās were handed down from one generation to another in the oral tradition. The Vedas were recited in continuous utterance called Saṁhitās. In order to preserve the Saṁhitās in form and content and hand them over to the next generation, there developed different modes of recitation. śaunaka provided the Padapāṭha of Ṛgvedasaṁhitā. It is an attempt to divide the continuous utterance of the Ṛgvedasaṁhitā into *padas* (words), thus preserving each and every word in isolation

removing euphonic combinations in its original accent. The Padapāṭha of the Yajurveda (Taittirīya Saṁhitā) is ascribed to ātreya, while that of the Sāmaveda to Gārgya. The Padapāṭhas also provide analysis of compound words by way of dividing it into constituent parts. This was certainly not a random division, A great thought of language analysis was applied in it. It is a systematic division of sentence into its words and words into its internal words arriving at the smallest meaningful word part. This exhibits the ever first model of constituent analysis. The Kramapāṭha mode of reciting was a peculiar ‘step by step’ arrangement of a Vedic text by combining the Saṁhitā and the Padapāṭha by giving the words both as connected and unconnected with following and preceding words to eliminate all possible errors. The eight Vedic *vikṛtis* (modifications) came into practice, viz. *śikhā, mālā, jaṭā, rekhā, dhvaja, daṇḍa, ratha* and *ghana*. These all amount to scientific analysis of language into its constituent parts and preserving the form and content at the same time.

Among the six Vedāṅgas, Nirukta (circa 400 BCE) ascribed to Yāska is particularly important for the aspect of content of the text. It is a commentary on the Nighaṇṭu (circa 400 BCE), a lexical kind of work which enumerates the Vedic words. However, it is not just jotting down of words but can be described as the foremost lexicon or dictionary that arranges synonyms belonging to different categories. The words falling in disuse were difficult to comprehend at a later period. Therefore, Nighaṇṭu made an attempt to collect such words and analyze them on semantic principles. For example, it begins with *gauḥ gmā kṣmā jmā* and so on. All these words are synonyms of earth. Similarly, 57 synonyms of *vāc* (speech) are provided in the text. The principles of dictionary making such as lemmatization, meaning-wise arrangement etc. could be traced in the collection of Nighaṇṭu. The Nirukta attempts at the word derivation. It tries to derive all the words from verbal roots. The five types of derivations are mentioned in Kāśikāvṛtti on Pāṇini 6.3.109:

*varṇāgamo varṇaviparyayaś ca dvau cāparau
varṇavikāranāśau |
dhātos tad arthātiśayena yogas tad ucyate pañcavidhami
niruktam ||*

“Augmentation, metathesis, the other two are substitution and elision of speech sound, connection with the verb on the basis of meaning, these are the five types of derivation.”

This actually refers to the chief phonological processes as procope, syncope, haplology, metathesis, anaptyxis of the modern linguistics.

Thus, in the early period of the first millennium BCE, there developed a tradition of language analysis with a purpose to preserve the sacred language of the Vedas. The pinnacle of language analysis was reached in the Aṣṭādhyāyī of Pāṇini (circa 400 BCE) which provided a comprehensive linguistic description of the Sanskrit language prevalent at his time. The Aṣṭādhyāyī included a set of rules and exceptions of generative nature. The rules in the Aṣṭādhyāyī are the brief expressions. Words are derived from them in a manner of input-output method. The application of one rule is input for the application of another rule. The Aṣṭādhyāyī is remarkable for its brevity, use of algebraic technical terms, metalanguage and certain devices for rule ordering. It is celebrated as the greatest monument of human intellect. Pāṇinian model inspired the later grammarians to develop more or less similar models with different purposes including Pali and Prakrit grammars also. The influence of Pāṇini continued to be so great that any word form not derivable in the Pāṇinian system was considered as incorrect. In a way, the Aṣṭādhyāyī of Pāṇini was instrumental in codifying the language variety of Sanskrit. This amounted to the preservation of Sanskrit language for centuries to come.

We thus find a systematic and scientific approach to the language study in the ancient works of the Vedāṅgas and other branches of knowledge in the Indian tradition. Copious literature on language study was to follow in other branches of the literature like Alaṅkāra (aesthetics) and Darśanas (philosophical systems). This study was done mainly on the availability of one single language, i.e. Sanskrit, but principles put in them have universal scope applicable to the general language study. The achievement of ancient Indians in the field of language study is commonly celebrated by the world today. The eminent western scholars beginning from Sir William Jones (18th CE), including Saussure (early 20th CE), Bloomfield (20th CE) were influenced by the achievements of ancient Indians in the field of language study. This all deserves deep and critical consideration while our nation is giving due emphasis on the Indian knowledge system in the New Educational Policy 2020.

References:

- Ghosh, Manmohan. 1938. *Pāṇinīya Śikṣā or the Śikṣā Vedaṅga Ascribed to Pāṇini (being the most ancient work on Indo-Aryan Phonetics)*. Calcutta: University of Calcutta.
- Joshi, Bhargavram. 1951. *Vyākaraṇamahābhāṣye Navāhnikam*. Mumbai: Nirnaysagar Press.
- Sontakke N.S. and C.G. Kashikar. 1946. *Rigveda-Samhita with the commentary of Sayanacarya. 4 Vols.* Poona: Vaidika Samshodhana Mandal.
- K. S. Varadacharya. 1969. *The Nyāyamañjarī of Jayantabhaṭṭa*. Mysore: University of Mysore, Oriental Research Institute Series, No. 116,139, vol.1,2.
- Swami Dwarkadas Shastri. 1967 *Nyāsa or Pañcikā Commentary of Ācārya Jinendrabuddhipāda and Padamañjarī of Haradatta Miśra on The Kāśikāvṛtti [Commentary on the Aṣṭādhyāyī of Pāṇini] of Vāmana-jayāditya. Part V.* Varanasi: Tara Publications.